

Weather Transition and People Health: A Baseline Survey in Patna

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Abstract: In this study it was estimated that how weather changes such as change in atmospheric pressure, temperature, and wind direction, along with seasonal changes change affects the human health. There was almost 60 percent increase in patient's inflows in OPDs and IPDs of those two hospitals during extreme heat and cold weather conditions. More patients suffered mortality and morbidity during the first wave of heat and cold wave. There could be a degree of acclimatization. Children get affected the more whereas gender orientation could not be estimated. Certainly homeless and laborers working outside homes were mostly affected.

Key words: Weather Transition; People Health in Bihar; Morbidity- Mortality and Weather in Bihar.

Introduction:

Bihar, a non-coastal and interior territory lying in the eastern part of India boundary by the states of Uttar Pradesh in the West, Jharkhand in the South, West Bengal in the East and Nepal in the North. Being a land lock territory, its public health requirement would be different from several coastal and hilly areas. The prevalence of diseases significantly differed due to different terrain. Bihar lies between 24° 20' and 27° -31' North latitude and 82° 19' and 88° 17' East longitude. With a total area of 94,163 square kilometers Bihar is the 12 largest states in India. Bihar has been divided by the river Ganges into two unequal parts, the north Bihar with an area of 53.3 thousand square km and the south Bihar has an area of 40.9 thousand square kilometers. Based on soil characterization, rainfall, temperature, and terrain, four main Agra-climatic zones in Bihar identified, such as Zone-I (North Alluvial Plain), Zone-II (North East Alluvial Plain), Zone-III A (South East Alluvial Plain), and Zone-III B (South West Alluvial Plain) each with its own unique features (Government, 2014).

Bihar plain is a vast stretch of rich and fertile land. Apart from the Ganges, fertile plains of Bihar drained by rivers like *Saryoo*, *Gandak*, *Sone*, *Punpun*, *Falgu*, *Karmanasa*, *Durgawati*, *Kosi*, *Ghaghara*, and many others. Floods are very common in the plains of Bihar and this enables constant deposition of silt, clay, and sand making the plains rich and fertile. The plain of Bihar covered by *Ganges* alluvial soil. To the north of Bihar within Nepal lie the Himalayan Mountains. Though the mountain range starts in Nepal, the Himalayas have influenced landforms and climate of Bihar. A series of small hills known as the *Rajgir* hills lay towards the central part of Bihar. The southern part of Bihar consists of *Kaimur* and *Chhotanagpur* plateaus.

Bihar has a continental monsoon type of climate. The presences of the Himalayas have a significant influence on the climate of Bihar, especially on the distribution of Monsoon

rains. The climate of Bihar divided into three main seasons. Cold weather season - December to February; Hot weather season - March to May; and Rainy Season - June to September. During winter the average temperature in Bihar could drop down to around 1-2° to 10° Celsius and during summer the average temperature could remain around 35° - 46° Celsius. Such large variation in weather created a different situation for *public health administration*.

The climate, season, and geographical conditions in Bihar created situations that could term as tropical and several diseases and casual ailments could identify emerging due to those tropical conditions. Further, several seasonal diseases and ailments keep emerging due to change of weather periodically. Bihar usually has larger weather transition periods that could repeat almost six times at least. During that transition of weather, rates of ailments tuned higher. Every season marked with specific disease occurrence. At the summer rate of dehydration, diarrhea, dysentery usually is increased. In the rainy season from July to September vector borne diseases like dengue, malaria, and encephalitis appeared most usual in several parts of the state. During that transition of climatic conditions, the evaluation of health expenditure could register significant enhancement. If winter could term good for health then rainy and summer definitely contributed morbidities in Bihar.

Seasonality always remained associated with the occurrence and pattern of diseases. In Bihar at the level of the State Health Society, a Disease Surveillance Unit has been set up under the aegis of *Integrated Disease Surveillance Project or IDSP* that conducted district wise data on the occurrence of diseases based upon surveillance of different laboratories. Epidemiologist of the unit deployed under the project submitted annual reports for all the districts in Bihar. In the year 2012, 600 cases of Hepatitis B, 2000 cases of Syphilis, and 182 cases of Gonococcus infections reported in Bihar. The cases recorded highest in the months of August, March, and March respectively (Society, 2012). In addition to that, the report also mentioned that Vector Borne Diseases like

Dengue, Malaria, Kala Azar, and Encephalitis occurred mostly during August to November. Likewise, almost all diseases have a particular seasonality and in addition district wide variety of diseases also recorded.

Survey of literature:

There are studies suggesting effects of weather on human health and most of those effects usually occurring during certain weather transition. Studies have also found that weather is associated with outbreaks of viral, bacterial infections, fever, diarrhea, nausea, headache, pneumonia, influenza, bronchitis, and is related to other morbidity effects linked high pollution levels. Weather has been also linked to changes in birth rates, and sperm counts. Large increases in mortality are reported during previous heat and cold waves. Humidity has an important impact on mortality since it contributes morbidity in the winter because cold, dry air leads to excessive dehydration of nasal passages and the upper respiratory tract and increased chance of microbial and viral infection. The precipitation in the form of rainfall is also associated with changes in mortality (Kalkstein, 1987).

Warmer temperatures, shifting rainfall patterns and increasing humidity affect the transmission of diseases by vectors like mosquitoes. They are quite sensitive to changes in temperature and rainfall and are among the first organisms to extend their range when environmental conditions become favorable. Thus, higher temperatures could influence the incidence of diseases such as malaria, dengue fever, yellow fever, and several types of encephalitis. Cold temperatures are often the limiting factor in mosquito survival, so any increase in minimum winter temperatures would likely extend mosquito ranges into temperate regions or higher altitudes where they do not survive.

Other vector-borne diseases such as *Schistosomiasis*, *Chagas disease*, *Sleeping sickness*, *river blindness*, and various strains of *encephalitis* all could change their ranges and patterns of infection in the course of climate change. Infectious diseases are emerging, resurging and undergoing redistribution on a global scale. Increase in temperature correlate with increased populations of some microorganisms that cause waterborne diseases, such as *Vibrio cholerae* bacterium, which causes *Cholera*. Higher ambient temperatures foster the growth of pathogens that thrive in or on food, such as *Salmonella*.

The impact of temperature on morbidity and mortality can be assessed at both the seasonal and daily level. The variability in occurrence of numerous illnesses is linked to somewhat predictable seasonal trends in temperature (Persinger, 1980). Medical disorders such as bronchitis, peptic ulcer, adrenal ulcer, glaucoma, goiter, eczema, and herpes zoster are related to seasonal variations in temperature (Tromp, 1963). Heart failure (most often myocardial infarction) and cerebrovascular accidents represent two general mortality

categories that have been correlated many times with ambient monthly temperatures (Persinger, 1980).

However, a majority of studies have also found that most of the excess deaths that occurred during periods of intense heat were not attributed to causes traditionally considered to be weather-related, such as heat stroke (M. Gover, 1938). Consequently, many researchers continue to utilize total mortality figures in their analyses, as deaths from a surprisingly large number of causes appear to escalate with increasing temperature (Applegate, et al., 1981) (Jones, 1982).

Through their studies Kutschenreuter (1959), Rogot (1973), Rogot (1973, MacFarlane and Waller, 1976 have preferred the use of maximum temperature as the primary predictor of mortality as well as average daily temperature as their primary weather statistic.

A number of studies compare death rates for extreme periods with those encountered during normal meteorological periods; this approach has met with some success (Oechsli and Buechley, 1970; Schuman et al., 1964; Schuman, 1972). An earlier work by Schuman (1972) includes smog as a related mechanism associated with fluctuations in death rate. One of the most commonly reported findings in heat wave-mortality studies involves the lag time between the temperature event and the mortality response. Temperature affects not only mortality, but also morbidity.

Factors found to be associated with an increased risk of heat stroke included alcoholism, living on higher floors of buildings, and the use of tranquilizers. Most research indicates that mortality rates during extreme heat vary with age, sex, and race. Oechsli and Buechley (1970) found that mortality rates during heat waves increase with age (Oechsli, 1970). Certain researchers have determined slight rises in mortality rates of infants during heat waves, but this is not a universal finding (Schuman, 1972). Studies relating mortality to gender also yield conflicting results. Large numbers of deaths during heat waves are found among poor inner-city residents who have little access to cooler environments (Jones et al., 1982).

Several studies have evaluated acclimatization as a factor contributing to heat-related deaths. Gover (1938) reported that excess mortality during a second heat wave in any year will be slight in comparison to excess mortality during the first, even if the second heat wave is unusually extreme. There is some research that implies that the effect of acclimatization has been overstated by many scientists. The use of the wind-chill index in winter and the temperature-humidity index in summer by many meteorologists seems to indicate that they believe acclimatization may have minimal impact on human activities. One cultural adjustment that may have an impact on heat wave-related mortality is the use of air conditioning. Kilbourne and other researchers, in an attempt to identify factors related to heat stroke, found a strong negative

relationship between daily hours of home air conditioning and heat-related mortality (Kilbourne, 1982). This finding is supported by Oechsli and Buechley (1970) in their study of heat-related deaths in Los Angeles. However, Ellis and Nelson (1978) have noted that during the past 30 years, mortality during heat waves in New York City has not changed significantly despite the increased use of air conditioning. Analysis by M. Marmor supports this finding; his study covering a 22-year period implied that air conditioning may be decreasing excess mortality during initial summer hot spells only (Marmor, 1975).

Methodology

The study was conducted at Patna during April 2014 to March 2015 involving a whole year of weather cycle. The respondents were the patients attending the outpatient department of two prominent hospitals in Patna namely Patna Medical College Hospital and Nalanda Medical College Hospital. The study was conducted on daily basis for the whole year and interviewed those patients taking medical advice. Almost 232 patients were interviewed considering their age, gender, income, and habitation.

There were at least six major weather transitions could be recorded in Bihar usually varied from one week to two or three weeks prior to ultimately a particular weather condition such as summer, rainy, and winter getting fully stabilized. Sometimes it takes long in weather acclimatization.

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However, acute heat, cold waves, and rainfall even contributed mortality and morbidity despite a level of acclimatization.

Findings

Despite the fact that there have been several literatures on impacts of weather on human health, there was no any such literature was available in Bihar. Therefore this finding would pave the way for several other researches to study the relationship of weather, weather acclimatization, and mortality and morbidity. The study have found that the numbers of patients increased by almost 63 percent during extreme cold and heat waves at the OPDs of both the Patna and Nalanda Medical College Hospitals. Most of them relieved after suggesting medicines and precautions and some of them admitted to IPDs as precaution to prevent further decline of conditions. It could not be ascertained that which age group or sex was more affected however children between 1-15 years seemingly affected the most. High humidity during the rainy season also contributed to the mortality and morbidity. Most such patients seemingly suffered due to a rapid changes in the weather. Even it was difficult for physicians to term certain ailment arising due to weather or weather changes nevertheless the number of patients at both hospitals increased more during extreme weather conditions of health, cold, and rain.